

Generations and Gender Survey (Round II)

Wave 2 Questionnaire

User module "Leaving and Returning to the Parental Home"

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User Modules in the GGS-II Wave 2 Questionnaire

The GGS-II Wave 2 questionnaire was restructured to include new thematic sections, with space allocated for user-driven innovations. In 2023, an open call invited researchers to submit new content modules. The proposals were evaluated by a selection committee based on their scientific novelty and relevance to the GGS.

Five user modules were selected and integrated into the questionnaire, offering fresh insights into family dynamics, fertility, and related topics. This working paper series contains revised versions of the original submissions, including the finalized questions that were ultimately incorporated into the Wave 2 questionnaire.

Andersson, G., Neyer, G., Lappegård, T., & Bujard, M. (2024). *User module: "Global Uncertainty and Institutional Trust"* (GGS-II Wave 2 Questionnaire). GGP Working Paper Series. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14044105

Berrington, A., & Perelli-Harris, B. (2024). *User module: "Leaving and Returning to the Parental Home"* (GGS-II Wave 2 Questionnaire). GGP Working Paper Series. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14044047

Billingsley, S., Mollborn, S., Olah, L., & Duvander, A.-Z. (2024). *User module: "Intensive Parenting"* (GGS-II Wave 2 Questionnaire). GGP Working Paper Series. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14043910

Mortelmans, D., Lück, D., Claessens, E., Van Gasse, D., Bujard, M., & Frembs, L. (2024). *User module: "Singlehood"* (GGS-II Wave 2 Questionnaire). GGP Working Paper Series. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14044075

Rouvroye, L., Fischer, M., Rampazzo, F., van der Vleuten, M., Fortes De Lena, F., Pao, C., de Vries, L., & Jin, Y. (2024). *User module: "Sexual Orientation"* (GGS-II Wave 2 Questionnaire). GGP Working Paper Series. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14044062

Abstract

In many countries, young adults have been leaving the parental home at later ages than previous generations. In addition, many adults who initially left the parental home subsequently returned. This module identifies movement in and out of the parental home between wave 1 and wave 2 and motivations for remaining, leaving and returning to the parental home. First, a single new question identifies whether the individual was living with at least one (biological/step/adoptive/foster) parent in wave 1. This information is then combined with the answers to existing wave 2 question MEM02 – relationship to other household members - to identify movement in and out of the parental home between wave 1 and wave 2. Depending upon the answers to these questions respondents are routed to a maximum of two new questions about their motivations for leaving/returning/remaining in the parental home. Given that these questions will be asked within the rich GGS framework we will be able to see how the dynamics of leaving and returning to the parental home are affected by country, gender, education and parental SES.

Motivation and scientific foundation

Relevance of the module

Residential independence from the parental home is generally a key life course event within the transition to young adulthood. Estimates from Labour Force Surveys suggest the share of young people aged 25 to 34 who live with their parents ranges widely across Europe, from four percent in Denmark, to more than half in Slovakia, Greece and Croatia (Eurostat, 2022). However cross-sectional data cannot tell us whether higher levels of co-residence in a country are due to fewer young adults leaving, or more young adults returning home (Stone et al., 2014). For this we need longitudinal data, such as the GGS (Coulter et al., 2020; Van den Berg et al., 2018). The European Social Survey (ESS) timing of life module did provide useful information on the year of first leaving home, but does not provide information on returns to the parental home (Chaloupkova, 2023). To understand large cross-national differences, we need better data on the likelihood of and motivations for leaving and returning home.

The GGS already collects (in wave 1) information on the month and year at first leaving home and intentions for leaving among those still co-resident with their parents. These data have been widely used (e.g. Schwanitz et al., 2017; Billari et al., 2019; Schwanitz et al., 2021). Previous work also exploited the panel element of round 1 of the GGS, comparing wave 1 intentions for leaving home with observed living arrangements in wave 2 to identify factors, including parental SES, associated with increased likelihood of achieving intentions (Billari et al. 2019). However, no existing cross-national research, based on GGS or any other survey, has analysed answers to direct questions about reasons for remaining, leaving or returning to the parental home.

The proposed module asks about motivations for remaining, leaving or returning to the parental home (depending on the respondent's experience). Some of the questions were piloted in the UK GGS w1 where they appear to have been well understood and did not cause any problems (Berrington & Perelli-Harris, 2024).

The inclusion of this module allows researchers to hear the reasons from participants themselves, rather than reasons being assumed based on an individuals' characteristics. Moreover, inter-generational co-residence is often discussed in a negative way, whereas co-residence has many benefits and can be normative in some cultural contexts. By including the motivation questions within an internationally comparative framework such nuances can be drawn out

Timeliness of Topic: Economic and Housing Uncertainty since 2008

Academic focus on transitions to residential independence is long standing, but has come to the fore once again following the 2008 recession and its particular impact on levels of economic uncertainty faced by young adults (See e.g. Gil-Solsona, 2023; Fuster et al., 2023). High levels of unemployment, under-employment and employment insecurity are prevalent in many high income countries (Palumbo et al., 2023) and hamper leaving home and family formation. Additionally, many young adults in high

income countries face high levels of housing unaffordability and inequality (James et al., 2024). In many high income countries wealth is passed intergenerationally through housing (Ronald and Arundel, 2023). Inequalities in the ability of the parental generation to help young adults financially and practically contribute to increased intra-generational inequalities. Thus, economic and housing uncertainty are key factors affecting the ability of young adults to attain residential independence from the parental home (Coulter et al., 2020).

Within a micro-macro perspective it is important to understand the role of individual, family and contextual factors (including youth labour market, housing markets, social norms) on patterns of leaving and returning home (Mandic, 2008). The GGP programme of surveys is ideally suited to provide this micro-macro perspective as we have information on country context, parental SES, and the individuals' own characteristics such as gender, education, employment status (Fokkema et al., 2016).

Questions already successfully tested in UK GGS

The questions on reasons for leaving home and for remaining in the parental home were cognitively tested by NATCEN for the UK GGS and provide a good range of answers (Appendix 1). There are very few refusals to these questions. Most people only gave one reason, but for those who gave more than one, the main reason question appears to work well (Berrington and Perelli-Harris, 2024). The only question that has not yet been tested is reasons for returning home. This is because this question is new to wave 2.

Policy relevance

Understanding the increased delay and reversibility of the transition to residential independence is important for policy. It is no longer possible just to collect one date of first leaving home, as if it were the start of a neat linear transition. We need to know whether delays in leaving and returns home are due to positive or negative reasons and how this differs by population sub groups e.g. gender, parental SES. There is policy interest as to the implications of young adults returning home for the wellbeing of both young adults and their parents (Tosi and Grundy, 2019). Data from the proposed GGS module will be able to identify how different reasons for inter-generational co-residence are related to the wellbeing of families. Finally, understanding factors inhibiting the transition to residential independence is important for understanding current housing needs in a country. In many high income countries decreasing headship rates among young adults is masking hidden homelessness and an unmet desire to live independently. Thus data from the GGS will be useful to inform housing projections (Berrington and Simpson, 2019).

Relevance to GGS-II wave 2 and all countries

Previous studies have found large cross-national differences in the age at leaving home and levels of inter-generational co-residence. We need to understand more about the dynamics of leaving and returning home in GGS countries as well as the underlying reasons. As described above, this module adds value to existing data collected within the GGS (both waves 1 and 2). All countries collect core data on living arrangements,

inter-generational co-residence, and intentions to leave the parental home. By including just three questions per respondent, we can identify the reasons underlying the transition and provide evidence in relation to the choices and constraints facing young adults in their living arrangements. Because these questions are included within the wider context of the GGS questionnaire we can examine reasons for leaving and returning home by country, gender, level of education, and parental socio-economic status, thus extending recent work, for example by Billari and colleagues (2019).

Levels of inter-generational co-residence differ considerably cross-nationally, and there are cultural norms as to the desirability of co-residence and appropriate ages for home leaving (Billari & Liefbroer, 2010). Nevertheless, we believe that these questions are appropriate for all GGS countries and they will enhance our understanding of cross-national differences.

Survey questions

b11PAR00 (Parents intro) (Empty)

The following questions are about your parents and grandparents.

IF (NOT(BHOUSEHOLD_MEMBERS.mumcores = yes))

b11GEN01 (Biological mother still alive (gen01)) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Is your biological mother still alive?

Yes, she is still alive

No, she is not alive anymore

ENDIF

IF (NOT(BHOUSEHOLD_MEMBERS.dadcores = yes))

b11GEN02 (Biological father still alive (gen02)) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Is your biological father still alive?

Yes, he is still alive

No, he is not alive anymore

ENDIF

IF ((b11GEN01 = 1)AND(b11GEN02 = 1))

b11GEN03 (Parents live together (gen03)) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Are your biological father and mother living together?

Yes

No

ENDIF

IF (b11GEN01 = 1)

b11GEN15A (Meetings with mother [FREQ] (gen15a)) (Empty)

How often do you meet with your biological mother in person?

You can choose to report the number of times per week, month or year.

Enter a number

NUMBER [0..365]

b11GEN15AU (Meetings with mother [UNIT] (gen15au)) (Never, DontKnow, Refusal)

times a...

Week

Month

Year

CHECK: (NOT((b11GEN15A = Empty)AND(b11GEN15AU = RESPONSE))) [Combination of answers is not allowed]

b11GEN15B (Contact with mother [FREQ] (gen15b)) (Empty)

How often do you have contact with your biological mother by phone, mail, email or any other electronic means?

You can choose to report the number of times per week, month or year.

Enter a number

NUMBER [0..365]

b11GEN15BU (Contact with mother [UNIT] (gen15bu)) (Never, DontKnow, Refusal)

times a...

Week

Month

Year

CHECK: (NOT((b11GEN15B = Empty)AND(b11GEN15BU = RESPONSE))) [Combination of answers is not allowed] IF ((b11GEN01 = 1)AND((b11GEN02 = 2)OR(b11GEN03 = 2)))

☐

b11GEN21 (Time to Mother's home) (DontKnow, Refusal)
How long does it normally take to get from your home to where your biological mother is living at present?
Please provide an answer in hours and minutes [HH:MM]
Vertical
99:99
STRING[4]

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF (b11GEN02 = 1)

☐

b11GEN29A (Meetings with father [FREQ] (gen29a)) (Empty)
How often do you meet with your biological father in person?
You can choose to report the number of times per week, month or year.

Enter a number
NUMBER [0..365]

b11GEN29AU (Meetings with father [UNIT] (gen29au)) (Never, DontKnow, Refusal)
times a...

Week
Month
Year

CHECK: (NOT((b11GEN29A = Empty)AND(b11GEN29AU = RESPONSE))) [Combination of answers is not allowed]

b11GEN29B (Contact with father [FREQ] (gen29b)) (Empty)
How often do you have contact with your biological father by phone, mail, email or any other electronic means?
You can choose to report the number of times per week, month or year.

Enter a number
NUMBER [0..365]

b11GEN29BU (Contact with father [UNIT] (gen29bu)) (Never, DontKnow, Refusal)
times a...

Week
Month
Year

CHECK: (NOT((b11GEN29B = Empty)AND(b11GEN29BU = RESPONSE))) [Combination of answers is not allowed] IF ((b11GEN02 = 1)AND((b11GEN01 = 2)OR(b11GEN03 = 2)))

☐

b11GEN35 (Time to Father's home) (DontKnow, Refusal)
How long does it normally take to get from your home to where your biological father is living at present?
Please provide an answer in hours and minutes [HH:MM]
Vertical
99:99
STRING[4]

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF (b11GEN03 = 1)

☐

b11GEN07 (Time to Parents' home) (DontKnow, Refusal)

How long does it normally take to get from your home to where your biological parents are living at present?

Please provide an answer in hours and minutes [HH:MM]

Vertical

99:99

STRING[4]

ENDIF

b11GEN54 (Grandparents alive [NUMBER] (gen54)) (None2, DontKnow, Refusal)

How many of your grandparents are alive?

NUMBER [0..10]

IF ((age > 40)AND(BKIDS.nkidstotal > 0))

☐

b11GEN55 (Has grandchild (gen55)) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Do you have any grandchildren?

Yes

No

IF (b11GEN55 = yes)

☐

b11GEN56 (Grandchildren [NUMBER] (gen56)) (DontKnow, Refusal)

How many grandchildren do you have?

NUMBER [1..99]

ENDIF

ENDIF

b11PAR10 (Whether living with at least one biological/step/adoptive/foster parent in wave 1) (DontKnow, Refusal)

At the time of the last survey (^auxFirstWaveMonthYear;), did you live in the same household as at least one of your parents? In this question and the following questions parents include biological, step, adoptive and foster parents.

Yes

No

IF (((b11PAR10 = no)AND(BHOUSEHOLD_MEMBERS.mumcores = no))AND(BHOUSEHOLD_MEMBERS.dadcores =

no))AND(BHOUSEHOLD_MEMBERS.adopt_step_fosterparentcores = no))

☐

b11PAR11A (Reasons for first stopping living with parent(s)) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Why did you first stop living with your parent(s)? Please choose all that apply to you.

SET OF

auxPar11a[1] := 'I went to college or university'

auxPar11a[2] := 'I started a job or apprenticeship'

auxPar11a[3] := 'I went travelling'

auxPar11a[4] := 'I wanted to live on my own or with friends'

auxPar11a[5] := 'I fell out with my parent(s)/they asked me to leave'

auxPar11a[6] := 'I got married or started to live with my partner'

auxPar11a[7] := 'I had a child/ became pregnant'

auxPar11a[8] := 'My parents' home was overcrowded'

auxPar11a[9] := 'My parent(s) moved out or died'

auxPar11a[10] := 'Other'

IF (count(b11PAR11A) > 1)

b11PAR11B (Main reason for first stopping living with parent(s)) (DontKnow, Refusal)

What is the main reason you first stopped living with your parent(s)?

auxPar11a[1] := 'I went to college or university'
auxPar11a[2] := 'I started a job or apprenticeship'
auxPar11a[3] := 'I went travelling'
auxPar11a[4] := 'I wanted to live on my own or with friends'
auxPar11a[5] := 'I fell out with my parent(s)/they asked me to leave'
auxPar11a[6] := 'I got married or started to live with my partner'
auxPar11a[7] := 'I had a child/ became pregnant'
auxPar11a[8] := 'My parents' home was overcrowded'
auxPar11a[9] := 'My parent(s) moved out or died'
auxPar11a[10] := 'Other'

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF (((b11PAR10 = yes)AND(BHOUSEHOLD_MEMBERS.mumcores = no))AND(BHOUSEHOLD_MEMBERS.dadcores = no))AND(BHOUSEHOLD_MEMBERS.adopt_step_fosterparentcores = no))

b11PAR12A (Reasons for stopping living with parent(s) between w1 and w2) (DontKnow, Refusal)

You said you were living with at least one biological/step/adoptive/foster parent at the time of the last survey, but now you are not. Why aren't you living with them anymore? Please choose all that apply to you.

SET OF

auxMoveReason2[1] := 'I went to college or university'
auxMoveReason2[2] := 'I left to start a job or apprenticeship'
auxMoveReason2[3] := 'I left to look for a (better) job'
auxMoveReason2[4] := 'I went travelling'
auxMoveReason2[5] := 'I got married or started to live with my partner'
auxMoveReason2[6] := 'I wanted to live on my own or with friends'
auxMoveReason2[7] := 'I fell out with my parent(s)/they asked me to leave'
auxMoveReason2[8] := 'I had a child /became pregnant'
auxMoveReason2[9] := 'My parents' home was overcrowded'
auxMoveReason2[10] := 'My parent(s) moved out or died'
auxMoveReason2[11] := 'Other'

IF (count(b11PAR12A) > 1)

b11PAR12B (Main reason for stopping living with parent(s) between w1 and w2) (DontKnow, Refusal)

What is the main reason you moved out?

auxMoveReason2[1] := 'I went to college or university'
auxMoveReason2[2] := 'I left to start a job or apprenticeship'

auxMoveReason2[3] := 'I left to look for a (better) job'
auxMoveReason2[4] := 'I went travelling'
auxMoveReason2[5] := 'I got married or started to live with my partner'
auxMoveReason2[6] := 'I wanted to live on my own or with friends'
auxMoveReason2[7] := 'I fell out with my parent(s)/they asked me to leave'
auxMoveReason2[8] := 'I had a child /became pregnant'
auxMoveReason2[9] := 'My parents' home was overcrowded'
auxMoveReason2[10] := 'My parent(s) moved out or died'
auxMoveReason2[11] := 'Other'

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF ((b11PAR10 = yes)AND(((BHOUSEHOLD_MEMBERS.mumcores = yes)OR(BHOUSEHOLD_MEMBERS.dadcores = yes))OR(BHOUSEHOLD_MEMBERS.adopt_step_fosterparentcores = yes)))

b11PAR13A (Reasons for still living with parent(s)) (DontKnow, Refusal)
What are the reasons you are living with your parent(s)? Please choose all that apply to you.

SET OF

auxStayReason[1] := 'Currently I cannot afford to live away from my parent(s)'
auxStayReason[2] := 'To save money first so that I can afford to buy or rent my own home'
auxStayReason[3] := 'It's more convenient for work/study'
auxStayReason[4] := 'I'm happy to live with my parents'
auxStayReason[5] := 'I don't feel ready to leave'
auxStayReason[6] := 'My parent(s) don't want me to move out at the moment'
auxStayReason[7] := 'My parent's/parents' health'
auxStayReason[8] := 'My partner's, my child(ren)'s, or my own health'
auxStayReason[9] := 'Other'

IF (count(b11PAR13A) > 1)

b11PAR13B (Main reason for living with parents in w1 and w2) (DontKnow, Refusal)

What is the most important reason you are living with your parent(s)?

auxStayReason[1] := 'Currently I cannot afford to live away from my parent(s)'
auxStayReason[2] := 'To save money first so that I can afford to buy or rent my own home'
auxStayReason[3] := 'It's more convenient for work/study'
auxStayReason[4] := 'I'm happy to live with my parents'
auxStayReason[5] := 'I don't feel ready to leave'
auxStayReason[6] := 'My parent(s) don't want me to move out at the moment'
auxStayReason[7] := 'My parent's/parents' health'
auxStayReason[8] := 'My partner's, my child(ren)'s, or my own health'
auxStayReason[9] := 'Other'

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF ((b11PAR10 = no)AND(((BHOUSEHOLD_MEMBERS.mumcores = yes)OR(BHOUSEHOLD_MEMBERS.dadcores = yes))OR(BHOUSEHOLD_MEMBERS.adopt_step_fosterparentcores = yes)))

b11PAR14A (Reason for living with parents in w2\ not living with parents in w1) (DontKnow, Refusal)

What is the reason you are living with your parent(s)? Please choose all that apply to you.

SET OF

auxStayReason2[1] := 'Currently I cannot afford to live away from my parent(s)'

auxStayReason2[2] := 'To save money first so that I can afford to buy or rent my own home'

auxStayReason2[3] := 'It's more convenient for work/study'

auxStayReason2[4] := 'I'm happy to live with my parents'

auxStayReason2[5] := 'I don't feel ready to leave'

auxStayReason2[6] := 'My parent(s) don't want me to move out at the moment'

auxStayReason2[7] := 'My parent's/parents' health'

auxStayReason2[8] := 'My partner's, my child(ren)'s, or my own health'

auxStayReason2[9] := 'I broke up with partner/spouse'

auxStayReason2[10] := 'I became unemployed'

auxStayReason2[11] := 'My studies came to an end'

auxStayReason2[12] := 'I returned from travelling'

auxStayReason2[13] := 'The accommodation I was living in is no longer available'

auxStayReason2[14] := 'Other'

IF (count(b11PAR14A) > 1)

b11PAR14B (Reason for living with parents in w2\ not living with parents in w1) (DontKnow, Refusal)

What is the main reason you are currently living with your parent(s)?

auxStayReason2[1] := 'Currently I cannot afford to live away from my parent(s)'

auxStayReason2[2] := 'To save money first so that I can afford to buy or rent my own home'

auxStayReason2[3] := 'It's more convenient for work/study'

auxStayReason2[4] := 'I'm happy to live with my parents'

auxStayReason2[5] := 'I don't feel ready to leave'

auxStayReason2[6] := 'My parent(s) don't want me to move out at the moment'

auxStayReason2[7] := 'My parent's/parents' health'

auxStayReason2[8] := 'My partner's, my child(ren)'s, or my own health'

auxStayReason2[9] := 'I broke up with partner/spouse'

auxStayReason2[10] := 'I became unemployed'

auxStayReason2[11] := 'My studies came to an end'

auxStayReason2[12] := 'I returned from travelling'

auxStayReason2[13] := 'The accommodation I was living in is no longer available'
auxStayReason2[14] := 'Other'

ENDIF
ENDIF

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Appendix 1: Unweighted frequencies from UK GGS wave 1 relating to ever leaving parental home (Gen52), reasons for first departure (GEN52b) and reasons for current coresidence (GEN53a).

GEN52 Ever left parental home	Percent	Freq.
0	3.66	261
1	96.34	6865

Total observations = 7126

GEN52b Reason for first leaving the parental home (First reason selected)	Percent	Freq.
Refused	2.61	179
Don't know	1.50	103
To go to college or university	34.48	2367
To start a job or training	8.68	596
To travel, e.g. for a gap year	3.22	221
I wanted to live on my own and could finally afford it	11.06	759
I fell out with my parent(s)/they asked me to leave	4.37	300
To marry or live with a partner/girlfriend/boyfriend	21.57	1481
To share with friends	2.11	145
I had a child /became pregnant	3.13	215
Parents' home was overcrowded	0.73	50
Other	6.54	449

Total observations =6865

GEN52b Reason for first leaving the parental home (Second reason selected)	Percent	Freq.
Nothing selected	93.20	6398
To go to college or university	0.32	22
To start a job or training	0.63	43
To travel, e.g. for a gap year	0.52	36
I wanted to live on my own and could finally afford it	1.24	85
I fell out with my parent(s)/they asked me to leave	0.39	27
To marry or live with a partner/girlfriend/boyfriend	1.75	120
To share with friends	0.55	38
I had a child /became pregnant	0.67	46
Parents' home was overcrowded	0.45	31
Other	0.28	19

Total observations =6865

GEN52b Reason for first leaving the parental home (Third reason selected)	Percent	Freq.
Nothing selected	98.83	6785
To go to college or university	0.07	5
To start a job or training	0.10	7

To travel, e.g. for a gap year	0.04	3
I wanted to live on my own and could finally afford it	0.16	11
I fell out with my parent(s)/they asked me to leave	0.06	4
To marry or live with a partner/girlfriend/boyfriend	0.28	19
To share with friends	0.17	12
I had a child /became pregnant	0.03	2
Parents' home was overcrowded	0.10	7
Other	0.15	10

Total observations =6865

GEN52b Reason for first leaving the parental home (Fourth reason selected)	Percent	Freq.
Nothing selected	99.83	6853
To go to college or university	0.01	1
To start a job or training	0.01	1
I wanted to live on my own and could finally afford it	0.06	4
To share with friends	0.01	1
I had a child /became pregnant	0.03	2
Other	0.04	3

Total observations =6865

GEN53a Reason for current coresidence (First reason selected)	Percent	Freq.
Refused	1.75	9
Don't know	1.95	10
Cannot afford to live away from parental home	34.11	175
To save money so that you can afford a deposit/mortgage/rent or other housing ex	17.15	88
It's more convenient for work/study	8.58	44
I'm happy to live with my parents/not ready to leave	14.42	74
Your parent(s) don't want you to move out at the moment	1.56	8
Your parent(s) require care	8.58	44
You or your dependents require care	2.53	13
Other	9.36	48

Total observations =513

GEN53a Reason for current coresidence (Second reason selected)	Percent	Freq.
Nothing selected	61.60	316
Cannot afford to live away from parental home	4.48	23
To save money so that you can afford a deposit/mortgage/rent or other housing ex	14.42	74
It's more convenient for work/study	6.43	33
I'm happy to live with my parents/not ready to leave	8.38	43

Your parent(s) don't want you to move out at the moment	2.14	11
Your parent(s) require care	0.97	5
You or your dependents require care	0.78	4
Other	0.78	4

Total observations =513

GEN53a Reason for current coresidence (Third reason selected)	Percent	Freq.
Nothing selected	78.36	402
Cannot afford to live away from parental home	1.17	6
To save money so that you can afford a deposit/mortgage/rent or other housing ex	2.73	14
It's more convenient for work/study	6.63	34
I'm happy to live with my parents/not ready to leave	5.65	29
Your parent(s) don't want you to move out at the moment	2.34	12
Your parent(s) require care	1.75	9
You or your dependents require care	0.58	3
Other	0.78	4

Total observations =513

GEN53a Reason for current coresidence (Fourth reason selected)	Percent	Freq.
Nothing selected	90.45	464
Cannot afford to live away from parental home	0.78	4
To save money so that you can afford a deposit/mortgage/rent or other housing ex	0.97	5
It's more convenient for work/study	0.39	2
I'm happy to live with my parents/not ready to leave	3.70	19
Your parent(s) don't want you to move out at the moment	2.14	11
Your parent(s) require care	0.58	3
You or your dependents require care	0.39	2
Other	0.58	3

Total observations =513

GEN53a Reason for current coresidence (Fifth reason selected)	Percent	Freq.
Nothing selected	98.25	504
Cannot afford to live away from parental home	0.19	1
Your parent(s) don't want you to move out at the moment	0.97	5
Your parent(s) require care	0.58	3

Total observations =513